

Oxidation of Some Hydroxy Acids by Bromine. Part I. The Light Reaction.

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The oxidation of tartaric acid by bromine was investigated by Ghosh and Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 165), and by Ghosh and Basu (*ibid.*, 1928, 5, 343). They find that the reaction shows an induction period and also an after-effect and the velocity increases rapidly with diminution in concentration of bromine. The induction period was already noticed by Bunsen and Roscoe (*Pogg. Annalen*, 1857, 100, 513 ; *Phil. Trans.*, 1857, 147, 355, 601).

The problem which, however, is of peculiar interest is the enormous increase in the unimolecular velocity constant with diminution in concentration of bromine. Ghosh and Basu (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 39) studied the oxidation of lactic acid by bromine but as they did it at only one concentration of the reactants, no information on the subject is available from their data.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The organic acids were all crystallised several times except lactic acid. Bromine was purified by distillation and freezing till of constant melting point. The lactic acid used was Merck's "very white extra pure" variety. In the preparation of the solutions conductivity water was always used.

The source of illumination was a 500 c.p. "point-o-lite" lamp and all the reactions were carried out in blue light using Plotnikow filters. The experimental arrangement is the same as described in other papers.

TABLE I.

Lactic acid = 0.363M. Bromine = 0.01128M. Temp. = 28.5°.

Time in minutes ...	0	40	65	72	80	90	100
(a-x) ...	13.7	11.0	9.0	7.6	6.1	4.75	3.55
k ₁ ...	Induction period	.0105	.0118	.0111	.0117		

TABLE II.

Lactic acid = 0.363M. Bromine = 0.0226M. Temp. = 28.5°.

Time in minutes	...	0	60	72	85	100	115	135
(a-x)	...	27.35	24.3	22.2	19.5	16.8	14.45	11.7
k_1	...	Induction period			.00434	.00432	.00432	.00442

TABLE III.

Mandelic acid = 0.31M. Bromine = 0.0232M. Temp. = 30°.

Time in minutes	...	0	10	25	38	45	52	59	71
(a-x)	...	30.2	28.0	25.1	20.4	16.4	13.0	10.6	7.4
k_1	...	Induction period			0.135	.0110	.0135	.0133	

TABLE IV.

Mandelic acid = 0.31M. Bromine = 0.0114M. Temp. = 30°.

Time in minutes	...	0	20	30	35	40	45	50
(a-x)	...	15.0	12.1	8.5	5.85	4.1	2.75	1.7
k_1	...	Induction period			.0324	.0317	.0327	.0341

TABLE V.

Phenyl lactic acid = 0.08M. Bromine = 0.0056M. Temp. = 16°.

Time in minutes	...	0	10	20	30	37	51
(a-x)	...	8.15	7.6	6.8	4.8	3.9	2.65
k_1	...	Induction period			.0150	.0142	.0135

TABLE VI.

Citric acid = 0.253M. Bromine = 0.011M. Temp. = 22°.

Time in minutes	...	0	15	30	44	55	70
(a-x)	...	11.0	10.5	9.65	8.6	8.0	7.3
k_1	...	Induction period			.0023	.0029	.0028

In the following tables a summary of the experimental results is given.

TABLE VII.

Influence of the concentration of bromine.

Temp.	Concentration of acids.	Concentration of bromine.	k_1	Ratio of bromine concentration.	Inverse ratio of velocity constants.
28.5°	0.363 M-	.0226M	.00435	2	2.5
	Lactic acid.	.01128M	.0111		
30°	0.31M-	.0232M	.0136	2.03	2.4
	Mandelic acid.	.0114M	.0327		
22°	0.253M-	.0112M	.0041	2.03	2.2
	Citric acid.	.0055M	.0088		
16°	0.08M-	.0085M	.0078	1.5	1.75
	Phenyl lactic acid.	.0056M	.0132		

TABLE VIII.

Influence of concentration of the reacting acids.

emp.	Conc. of bromine.	Conc. of acids.	k_1	Ratio of the concentration of acid.	Ratio of velocity constants.
28.5°	0.0226M	.533 M-Lactic acid.	.00607	1.47	1.35
	"	.363 M- "	.00435		
	0.0118 M	.533 M- "	.0144	1.47	1.3
	0.0113 M	.363 M- "	.0111		
30°	0.0232 M	.31 M- Mandelic acid.	.0136	1.5	1.4
	"	.465 M- "	.019		
16°	.0056 M	.08 M-Phenyl lactic acid.	.0132	1.6	1.4
	.0056 M	.06 M "	.0095		

TABLE IX.

Influence of intensity of incident light.

Temp.	Conc. of acids.	Conc. of bromine.	k_1 .	Ratio of velocity constants.	Ratio of square root of intensity.
22°	0·46 M-Lactic acid.	·0188 M	·0167	} 1·46	1·6
	„	·0186 M	·0245		
23°	0·253 M-Citric acid.	·011 M	·00283	} 1·45	1·5
	„	·0112 M	·0041		
30°	0·31 M-Mandelic acid.	·0292 M	·0086	} 1·6	1·4
	„	„	·0136		
	„	„	·0114 M	·0230	} 1·42
„	„	·0112 M	·0327		

TABLE X.

Influence of temperature.

Temp.	Conc. of acid.	Conc. of bromine.	k_1 .	Temp. coeff.
22°	·46 M-Lactic acid.	·0188 M	·0167	} 1·68
32°	„	„	·0284	
22°	·267 M-Mandelic acid.	·0152 M	·0174	} 1·8
32°	„	„	·0313	

The dark reaction in the case of phenyl lactic acid and bromine is quite considerable which is given in the following table.

TABLE XI.

Phenyl lactic acid = 0·08 M. Bromine = 0·00558 M. Temp. = 16°.

Time in minutes	...	0	25	50	83	115	165	250
($d-x$)	...	8·05	7·1	6·5	5·9	5·5	4·85	3·9
k_2	...	Initial	·00154	·00149	00123	·00119	·00115	
							Mean	·00132

With the same concentration of bromine and the acid, k_1 has a value 0·0049 at 26° ; thus giving a high temperature coefficient of

3.9. The mean velocity constants due to the dark reactions have been deducted from the light reactions given in Table VII, IX and X. In the above table k_1 has been calculated by taking 7.1 as the initial reading because the induction period in the light reaction disappears when $(a-x)$ falls to near about this value.

TABLE XII.

Dark reaction.

Temperature—22°.

		Mandelic acid=0.235M. Bromine=0.014M.					
Time in hours. ...	0	'75	3	7	19.25		
(a-x)	... 17.6	16.4	14.6	12.7	8.7		
		Lactic acid=0.239M. Bromine=0.139M.					
Time in hours. ...	0	'75	2.7	7.25	19.5	47	
(a-x)	... 17.4	17.0	16.7	16.0	14.4	10.8	
		Citric acid=.282M. Bromine=.0139M.					
Time in hours. ...	0	'75	2.83	7.5	19.33	47	
(a-x)	... 17.35	16.9	16.5	15.7	14.1	12.1	

It is evident that the velocity of dark reactions is small compared with light reaction and there is absolutely no induction period.

Application of Einstein's Law of Photochemical Equivalence.

It can be seen from the results that the velocity of the light reactions depends, to a large extent, on the concentration of bromine as well on the reacting acids. The reactions have a high temperature coefficient and also an induction period. So it is obvious that this law will not be applicable to these cases. For the sake of comparison, however, the number of quanta that bring about the transformation of a molecule of bromine in the case of each of these reactions is given in Table XIII. For the purpose of calculation, the quantity of bromine which disappeared in a certain interval after the period of induction was over, has been taken into consideration.

With 0.46M-lactic acid and 0.0188M-bromine, the change in the concentration of bromine was 0.01275M to 0.0055M in 21 mins.

The intensity of blue light just behind the reaction cell ($4 \times 4 \times 10$ cm.) filled with water is $4.2/2.2 \times 900$ ergs. per sec. per sq.

cm., and when the same cell is filled with 0.00912M (*i.e.*, 0.01275—0.0055/2M) bromine solution the intensity of light behind it is $1.8/2.2 \times 900$ ergs. per sec. per sq. cm.

$$\therefore \text{The energy absorbed is } \frac{(4.2 - 1.8)}{2.2} \times 900 \text{ ergs.}$$

The number of quanta of blue light of average wave-length $470\mu\mu$ is

$$\frac{\frac{2.4}{2.2} \times 900 \times 470 \times 10^{-7}}{6.5 \times 10^{27} \times 3 \times 10^{16}} = 2.37 \times 10^{14}.$$

The number of molecules transformed

$$= \frac{(0.01275 - 0.0055) \times 6.1 \times 10^{27}}{21 \times 60 \times 1000} = 35.1 \times 10^{14}.$$

$$\frac{\text{No. of mols. transformed}}{\text{No. of quanta absorbed}} = 15 \text{ (approx.).}$$

TABLE XIII.

Blue light of average wave-length $470\mu\mu$.

Temp.	Initial conc. of acid.	Initial conc. of bromine.	Amount of bromine transformed in gm. mols.	Time required for the trans-formation (mins.).	No. of quanta absorbed.	No. of mols. trans-formed.	No. of mols. No. of quanta.
22°	.46M-Lactic acid	.0188M	.00725	21	2.37×10^{14}	35.1×10^{14}	15
„	.265M-Mandelic acid	.0152M	.00685	24	2.25×10^{14}	29.0×10^{14}	13
„	.259M-Citric acid	.011M	.00234	40	2.25×10^{14}	6.75×10^{14}	3
15°	.08M-Phenyl lactic acid	.0056M	.00243	31	6.35×10^{14}	8.0×10^{14}	13

The reaction cell used in the reaction between bromine and phenyl lactic acid had the dimensions $4 \times 4 \times 2$ cm. and 3 c.c. of the reaction mixture were titrated each time, and in the case of other acids a $4 \times 4 \times 1$ cm. cell was used and the volume of reaction mixture titrated was 2 c.c.

From the foregoing tables it will be found that the velocity varies inversely as the concentration of bromine and is nearly proportional to the concentration of the acids. Calculation on this basis will make it evident that for a constant concentration of bromine and equimolecular concentrations of the acids, the number of molecules transformed per quantum of energy absorbed come out to be the largest in the case of phenyl lactic acid and smallest in the case of citric acid. Mandelic acid comes second and lactic acid third in order. It is quite interesting to see that the velocities of the dark reactions are also in the same order (Tables XI and XII).

Cassel (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1916, **92**, 113) also found a similar behaviour in the decomposition of chlor- and brom-acetic acids in ultraviolet light. Bromoacetic acid has got a higher rate of decomposition both in light and in darkness.

Discussion.

Bromination and oxidation processes in which bromine takes part go to show that it is the bromine atom which is responsible for photochemical reactions. Experiments of Bodenstein and Berthoud also point to the same thing and in such reactions the velocity varies as the square root of the intensity of incident radiation. The first stage in the reaction is, therefore, the activation of bromine molecules by the absorption of light.

Ghosh and Basu (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 343, 361) have suggested that the rapid rise in the velocity with diminution in concentration of bromine is due to the de-activation of the bromine atoms by collision with oxygen molecules present in the system in the dissolved state and also held in equilibrium due to the reaction,

It has been shown in a recent paper ((Purakayastha, *loc. cit.*) that this anomalous behaviour disappears in presence of a bromide or hydrobromic acid. It is easy to see that the amount of free bro-

mine in a solution containing sufficient bromide will be very small owing to the reaction,

and also the rate of the reaction (2) will be exceedingly small due to the inertness of Br_3^- ions in darkness as well as in light. (A paper on the function of Br_3^- ions in photochemical reactions appears in this issue of the *Journal*). The amount of oxygen due to reaction (2) will be much less in presence of HBr which, in addition, quite considerably increases the concentration of this component on the right hand side of equation (2). These facts, in a way, support the view put forward by Ghosh and Basu ; but it seems, probably this is not all. In a series of experiments with mandelic acid and bromine in presence of potassium bromide, the ratio, total Br_2/KBr was kept practically the same. The concentration of total bromine and free bromine varied from 0.0087 M to 0.0215 M and 0.0054 M to 0.0096 M respectively and the ratio, total Br_2/KBr was 1:5. As the concentration of total bromine as well as free bromine vary quite appreciably, it was expected that the velocity constants would increase with diminution in the concentration of bromine. The experimental results, however, show that the reaction velocity is solely determined by the ratio, free $\text{Br}_2/\text{Br}_3^-$ quite irrespective of the concentration of total bromine or free bromine.

The experimental facts justify the assumption that the induction period is due to the formation of complexes by the interaction of the reactants or the existence of a solvent bromine complex. It should be stated in this connection that though the induction period disappears in presence of sufficient potassium bromide, it persists in presence of an equivalent concentration of hydrobromic acid. This leads to the view that probably a complex is formed by the interaction of bromine and the reacting acid. Hydrobromic acid increases the acid-bromine complex by throwing back the dissociation of the weak reacting acids whereas KBr may increase the ionisation and thus cause a further diminution in the concentration of the complex.

It has been found that the negative ions of the acids are reactive and a large number of molecules are transformed per quantum of energy absorbed. It is obvious, therefore, that the active bromine

atom is regenerated in the process. It is probable that an intermediate complex is formed by the reaction between the active bromine atoms and the negative ions of the acids which are subsequently oxidised by collision with bromine molecules with the liberation of the active bromine atoms.

Summary.

(1) The unimolecular velocity constants with respect to bromine are nearly proportional to the concentration of the reacting acids.

(2) The same constants vary nearly inversely as the concentration of bromine.

(3) The same constants vary as the square root of the intensity of incident radiation.

(4) The reactions have an induction period and also an after-effect. The after-effect in the case of mandelic acid and phenyl lactic acid was shown by Purakayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 721) and in the case of citric acid and lactic acid by Dhar and Mukerje (*ibid*, 1925, 2, 277).

(5) The induction period disappears in presence of potassium bromide.

(6) A fairly large number of bromine molecules is transformed in each case, per quantum of energy absorbed.

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